

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe

Towards Sustainable Development

D1.4. Open Research Data Pilot

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
Project Title	<i>Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development</i>
Grant Agreement No.	873119
Deliverable Reference Number	D1.4
Work Package	1
Deliverable Title	Open Research Data Pilot
Dissemination Level	Public
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Editor(s)	Wulf Reiners
Version	1.0
Date	30 June 2020

Overview

PRODIGEES commits to Horizon 2020's Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP). The PRODIGEES Consortium understands the ORDP's mission to "maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects" (<https://ec.europa.eu>). The maxim of the ORDP, "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" balances the accessibility of scientific research against commercialisation, privacy, and security. The researcher and research interests are protected while allowing the maximum potential for scientific innovation.

PRODIGEES adheres to the ORDP principles of **findable**, **accessible**, **interoperable** and **reusable** (FAIR). Proficient data management allows for each of the FAIR principles to be achieved with ease while fostering a culture of openness and innovation. PRODIGEES' Data Management Plan (D1.2) provides a detailed account of PRODIGEES' data management methods used to implement the action.

A distinction needs to be made between the research data and research publications. PRODIGEES research data will adhere to the aforementioned conditions of the FAIR principles of the ORDP's mission. Similarly, PRODIGEES research publications will be published as open access. Open access publications will be published either through a channel of PRODIGEES' partner institutes, or by a third party, as described in the International Database for Dissemination and Communication (D4.2) and elaborated upon in the Report on Implementation of Dissemination and Communication Strategy (D4.6). In either case, the publication will be open access and freely available to the public for exploitation, advancement, and further dissemination.

For fulfilling the goals of the ORDP, PRODIGEES administers the following measures:

- 1) Developing and continuously updating a comprehensive DMP.
- 2) Depositing research data and open access publications into an online repository.
- 3) Ensuring that third parties can freely exploit, advance, and disseminate research data.
- 4) Providing traceable evidence so that the raw data of the research may be validated.
- 5) Integrating the ORDP's requirements into individual researchers' projects via a 'Researcher Flow-Chart'.

The ORDP applies directly to the data (metadata and raw data) which is used to validate scientific research results. By ensuring the above conditions, PRODIGEES guarantees the maxim of the ORDP as well as the FAIR principles in the use and dissemination of data.

PRODIGEES takes advantage of its vast communication and dissemination network in order to ensure that research data and research results are FAIR. Research data and results are actively publicised through in-house publishing channels, workshops, seminars, lectures, newsletters, and networking.

The following are the four specific conditions fostered by PRODIGEES for implementing the action within the framework of the ORDP.

1. Developing and continuously updating a comprehensive DMP

PRODIGEES' DMP (Deliverable 1.2) describes the life cycle for data collected, processed, and generated by PRODIGEES. The DMP describes how research data is handled during and after the project, *what* data is handled, *which* methodologies are applied, how the data will be made open access, and how the data will be preserved and/or destroyed.

The PRODIGEES DMP ensures that data handled during PRODIGEES is high quality, safe, sustainable, accessible, and reusable. It provides a data handling and processing strategy for PRODIGEES staff and researchers. It also highlights the costs and resources for implementing the action within the ORDP framework.

The PRODIGEES DMP creates the structures for adhering to PRODIGEES ethical guidelines, as laid out in the Grant Agreement. It also details the strategy for data security, privacy, and protection, with a distinct structure of accountability.

Importantly, the DMP is a living document which updates and changes as the project updates and changes.

2. Depositing research data and open access publications into an online repository

PRODIGEES uses the [Zenodo](#) platform as its online repository for research data and open access publications which have been released by the original publisher. The PRODIGEES Steering Committee unanimously agreed to use Zenodo as PRODIGEES' online repository during its May 27, 2020 Steering Committee Meeting, following a discussion which began on March 30, 2020 at the PRODIGEES Kickoff Meeting. Zenodo was chosen for its applicability to open access publications and open data storage, for its broad acceptance in the Horizon 2020 community, and its accessibility from all of PRODIGEES' partner countries. The repository is named, "PRODIGEES Research Community". Links to the Zenodo repository are embedded in the project website, as well as updates through PRODIGEES' dissemination channels. The uploads to the PRODIGEES Research Community are curated by the PRODIGEES Project Manager.

3. Ensuring that third parties can freely exploit, advance, and disseminate research data

Per the FAIR principles of the ORDP, the PRODIGEES Consortium ensures that PRODIGEES research data is not only accessible, but highly promoted. Relevance is a determining factor of ease of access. PRODIGEES dissemination channels actively reproduce links to PRODIGEES research data and publications, through the PRODIGEES Website (D4.1), the Newsletter (D4.3), and social media. Furthermore, Work Package 4 (WP4), Implementation of Dissemination and Communication Strategy, provides concepts for two Transnational Open Access Trainings (D4.5), two Policy Labs (D4.7), a Joint R&I Agenda and Action Plan for Improved Continuous Cooperation (D4.8), and a Final Conference (D4.9), scheduled to take place at PRODIGEES partner institute, Instituto Mora, in Mexico City. Each of these project-wide activities are

publicised events which promote the research of PRODIGEES as well as each individual researcher's contributions, ensuring that the research data is disseminated maximally.

4. Providing traceable evidence so that the raw data of the research may be validated

As detailed in the DMP, raw data and 'data-in-progress' is stored on the Zenodo platform in the form of PRODIGEES researcher obligations. These obligations include, one publishable work, two lecture/seminar/workshops, contribution to the Newsletter, a Digital Knowledge Product, and a Future Action Plan. All raw data from any and all of the researcher obligations will be made available upon on the Zenodo platform. Further data requests can be made to the PRODIGEES Project manager or the individual researcher, with an obligation to respond in adherence with the open access prerogative of the ORDP.

5. Integrating the ORDP's requirements into individual researchers' projects via a 'Researcher Flow-Chart'

From the outset of the project, PRODIGEES staff created a comprehensive and standardized infrastructure for organising documentation, including the documentation used by PRODIGEES researchers and partner institutes. A 'Researcher Flow-Chart' is an organisational document which provides a framework of tasks for each individual researcher during the implementation of their secondment. The framework is organised into three tiers, Before, During, and After. Each tier of the framework provides a checklist of to-dos, reminders, and obligations, with details about how to carry out the specific task. Following the framework established by the Researcher Flow Chart, each researcher is guaranteed to successfully complete and record the secondment while fulfilling the mandate of the ORDP.

